

DESIGNING WITH ANISOTROPY.

PART 3 :

QUASI-HOMOGENEOUS ANISOTROPIC LAMINATES.

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SUMMARY : In this paper, we show the existence of a particular class of solutions to the problem of quasi-homogeneous laminates, that is laminates that have the same behaviour in stretching and in bending, with no coupling. We call quasi-trivial this type of solutions, to emphasise the fact that it is not necessary to solve directly the equations governing the problem of quasi-homogeneity to find them. A very special feature of this class of solutions is the fact that no predetermined orientation is fixed for the plies. A surprising result is the existence of a great number of solutions.

KEYWORDS : laminates, uncoupling, quasi-homogeneity, polar representation, plane tensors, composites design, inverse problems.

INTRODUCTION.

It is well known by the designers of composite structures that a laminate made of anisotropic, but identical, plies has not, generally speaking, the same behaviour in bending and in stretching, and moreover there is a coupling between these two responses.

At present, no general rule is known to design laminates that behave like homogeneous materials. The problem of uncoupling is presented in Part 2, while in this Part 3 we consider the problem of finding an uncoupled laminate that has also the same equivalent elastic properties in membrane and bending behaviour.

This aspect has been rather neglected for a long period. It seems that the existence of such laminates has even not been suspected until the work of Verchery and his co-authors. In 1988, Kandil & Verchery [7] gave some sufficient conditions to obtain the same in-plane and flexural behaviour, with limited examples.

So we were lead to define the concept of quasi-homogeneous laminates, as laminated plates with the same elastic behaviour as classical homogeneous plates, i.e. without coupling and

with the same elastic behaviour in bending and in stretching. Such materials have a much simpler behaviour than ordinary laminates, while retaining the advantages of composites.

Still starting by the polar representation theory of in-plane elasticity tensors, we consider herein the general problem of quasi-homogeneity, and formulate the equations that govern the problem. It is rapidly recognised that these equations are non-linear, like often in inverse problems, even in linear elasticity. Though the non linearity of the system of governing equations be low, as it is composed of linear and quadratic equations, it appears immediately that a complete solution of such a system is in general a very hard task.

Fortunately, thanks to the very special structure of the equations, we have been able to find a particular class of solutions, rather general, easy to be detected and surprisingly populated by a great number of solutions. To recognise the fact that these solutions are found with no need to solve directly the governing equations, we have called them quasi-trivial.

The quasi-trivial solutions have some important properties. The most important one, especially for applications, is the fact that they determine only a stacking sequence, the plies forming groups with no defined orientation.

Thermoelastic properties are also investigated in the paper, and we show how the two classes of quasi-trivial solutions for elastic and thermoelastic properties coincide perfectly, which is a very important feature for applications.

The paper ends with results of experimental tests performed, which perfectly confirm and illustrate the predictions.

LAMINATES BEHAVIOUR BY POLAR TENSORS REPRESENTATION.

When a plate is composed superposing various plies, the behaviour of the laminate is given by the so called Classical Laminated Plate Theory (CLPT), based upon the well-known hypotheses of Kirchhoff-Love (see for instance [1], [2], [3], [4]). The mechanical behaviour of the plate is so condensed in the equation :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 \\ \boldsymbol{\chi} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{N} is the vector of membrane forces and \mathbf{M} that of the bending moments, while $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0$ and $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ are respectively the vectors of middle plane strains and curvatures. The tensors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{D} describe the membrane and the flexural behaviour, while \mathbf{B} takes into account the coupling between membrane and bending. For a general sketch like in Fig. 1, the components of \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} are ($N=2p+1$ if odd and $N=2p$ if even) :

$$\mathbf{A} = \sum_{k=-p}^p (z_{k+1} - z_k) \mathbf{Q}_k; \quad \mathbf{B} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=-p}^p (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2) \mathbf{Q}_k; \quad \mathbf{D} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=-p}^p (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3) \mathbf{Q}_k. \quad (2)$$

Here, \mathbf{Q} is the classical tensor relating stresses to strains in two dimensional elasticity. It is well known that express the above tensors in rotated frames is rather complicate in Cartesian co-ordinates. To this purpose, and in order to obtain simplifications, we will use the so-called polar representation of fourth-order plane tensors developed and used by Verchery and his co-workers ([5] - [10], and also Parts 1 and 2, in these same proceedings). This polar method incorporates in a more systematic and powerfull way known results and methods such as those introduced by Tsai and Pagano ([3] and [11]). The components of a generic fourth-order plane tensor \mathbf{L} , having the symmetries of elasticity, can be expressed as :

Figure 1: General sketch; a) odd number of plies; b) even number of plies.

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{1111} &= T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0 + 4R_1 \cos 2\Phi_1; \\
 L_{1122} &= -T_0 + 2T_1 - R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0; \\
 L_{2222} &= T_0 + 2T_1 + R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0 - 4R_1 \cos 2\Phi_1; \\
 L_{1212} &= T_0 - R_0 \cos 4\Phi_0; \\
 L_{1112} &= R_0 \sin 4\Phi_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\Phi_1; \\
 L_{2212} &= -R_0 \sin 4\Phi_0 + 2R_1 \sin 2\Phi_1.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

We can obtain in this way :

i. polar components of tensor \mathbf{A} for a laminate :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{T}_0 &= \sum_{k=-p}^p T_{0k} (z_{k+1} - z_k); \\
 \bar{T}_1 &= \sum_{k=-p}^p T_{1k} (z_{k+1} - z_k); \\
 \bar{R}_0 e^{4i\hat{\Phi}_0} &= \sum_{k=-p}^p R_{0k} e^{4i(\Phi_{0k} + \delta_k)} (z_{k+1} - z_k); \\
 \bar{R}_1 e^{2i\hat{\Phi}_1} &= \sum_{k=-p}^p R_{1k} e^{2i(\Phi_{1k} + \delta_k)} (z_{k+1} - z_k);
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

ii. polar components of tensor \mathbf{B} for a laminate :

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{T}_0 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=-p}^p T_{0k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2); \\
\hat{T}_1 &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=-p}^p T_{1k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2); \\
\hat{R}_0 e^{4i\hat{\Phi}_0} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=-p}^p R_{0k} e^{4i(\Phi_{0k} + \delta_k)} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2); \\
\hat{R}_1 e^{2i\hat{\Phi}_1} &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=-p}^p R_{1k} e^{2i(\Phi_{1k} + \delta_k)} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2);
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

iii. polar components of tensor \mathbf{D} for a laminate :

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{T}_0 &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=-p}^p T_{0k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\
\tilde{T}_1 &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=-p}^p T_{1k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\
\tilde{R}_0 e^{4i\tilde{\Phi}_0} &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=-p}^p R_{0k} e^{4i(\Phi_{0k} + \delta_k)} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\
\tilde{R}_1 e^{2i\tilde{\Phi}_1} &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=-p}^p R_{1k} e^{2i(\Phi_{1k} + \delta_k)} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3);
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here, the angles Φ_{0k} and Φ_{1k} are the angles defined for the ply k by its own reference frame, and δ_k is the angle that such frame forms with the global reference frame of the laminate. By Eqs. (3), the components of tensors \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{D} for the laminates may be obtained as functions of the above final components T_0 , etc.

QUASI-HOMOGENEOUS LAMINATES

Mathematically speaking, a quasi-homogeneous laminate, that is a laminate which behaves like an homogeneous material in the linear elastic range, is characterised by the following two properties:

$$\frac{\mathbf{A}}{h} = 12 \frac{\mathbf{D}}{h^3}; \quad \mathbf{B} = \mathbf{0}. \tag{7}$$

In the preceding equations, h is the total thickness of the plate. As already said, we will deal in the following with laminates composed of identical plies, that is of plies with the same physical properties and thickness. In such a case, Eqs. (4), (5) and (6) are considerably simplified, and it can be easily seen that :

$$\bar{T}_0 = \tilde{T}_0 = T_0; \quad \bar{T}_1 = \tilde{T}_1 = T_1; \quad \hat{T}_0 = \hat{T}_1 = 0. \tag{8}$$

and :

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{R}_0 e^{4i\bar{\Phi}_0} &= R_0 e^{4i\Phi_0} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{4i\delta_k}; \\
\bar{R}_1 e^{2i\bar{\Phi}_1} &= R_1 e^{2i\Phi_1} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k}; \\
\hat{R}_0 e^{4i\hat{\Phi}_0} &= \frac{1}{2} R_0 e^{4i\Phi_0} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{4i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2); \\
\hat{R}_1 e^{2i\hat{\Phi}_1} &= \frac{1}{2} R_1 e^{2i\Phi_1} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2); \\
\tilde{R}_0 e^{4i\tilde{\Phi}_0} &= \frac{1}{3} R_0 e^{4i\Phi_0} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{4i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\
\tilde{R}_1 e^{2i\tilde{\Phi}_1} &= \frac{1}{3} R_1 e^{2i\Phi_1} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3).
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Finally, the quasi-homogeneity conditions (7), by virtue of equations (8) and (9), become simply :

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{h} \bar{R}_0 e^{4i\bar{\Phi}_0} = \frac{12}{h^3} \tilde{R}_0 e^{4i\tilde{\Phi}_0} &\Rightarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{4i\delta_k} = \frac{4}{h^3} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{4i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\
\frac{1}{h} \bar{R}_1 e^{2i\bar{\Phi}_1} = \frac{12}{h^3} \tilde{R}_1 e^{2i\tilde{\Phi}_1} &\Rightarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} = \frac{4}{h^3} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\
\hat{R}_0 e^{4i\hat{\Phi}_0} = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{4i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2) = 0; \\
\hat{R}_1 e^{2i\hat{\Phi}_1} = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2) = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Introducing the tensor :

$$\mathbf{C} = \frac{\mathbf{A}}{h} - 12 \frac{\mathbf{D}}{h^3}, \tag{11}$$

the quasi-homogeneity conditions, equations (11), become simply :

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{C}(e^{4i\delta_k}) = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=k^*}^p c_k (e^{4i\delta_k} + e^{4i\delta_{-k}}) = 0; \\
\mathbf{C}(e^{2i\delta_k}) = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=k^*}^p c_k (e^{2i\delta_k} + e^{2i\delta_{-k}}) = 0; \\
\mathbf{B}(e^{4i\delta_k}) = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=k^*}^p b_k (e^{4i\delta_k} - e^{4i\delta_{-k}}) = 0; \\
\mathbf{B}(e^{2i\delta_k}) = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=k^*}^p b_k (e^{2i\delta_k} - e^{2i\delta_{-k}}) = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Here $k^* = 0$ if N is odd, and $k^* = 1$ if it is even. The coefficients c_k and b_k are given by the following rules :

$$\begin{aligned}
c_k &= p(p+1) - 3k^2, \quad b_k = k \quad \text{for } N \text{ odd}; \\
c_k &= (p-1)(p+1) - 3k(k-1), \quad b_k = 2k-1 \quad \text{for } N \text{ even}.
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Equations (12) are the system to solve in the search for quasi-homogeneous laminates composed of identical plies. As it can be noticed, such a property does not depend upon the mechanical properties of the single ply, as it was to be expected.

In order to fix a solution, the orientation of one of the plies must be fixed *a priori*. In the following, we will consider that the first ply from the bottom has $\delta = 0$.

It is an easy task to verify that the trivial solution, that is the solution which gives the same orientation for each ply in a laminate, is possible for each N .

THE CLASS OF QUASI-TRIVIAL SOLUTIONS.

No general solution of system (12) is presently available. Nevertheless, a particular class of solutions is rather easy to be found, once and for all, for each laminate : we will call such class the *set of quasi-trivial solutions* of the problem of quasi-homogeneity.

The existence of a particular class of solutions to system (12) is suggested by some peculiar properties of coefficients c_k and b_k , in Eqs. (13). In fact, it can be noticed easily that coefficients c_k are symmetric about the middle plane, while coefficients b_k are anti-symmetric (which suggests immediately the well-known rule of symmetrical stacking sequences for uncoupled laminates), and they are linearly increasing from the lower to the upper ply. Moreover, the sum of them is zero, in both cases.

So, if we assume that a group is composed by a certain number of plies having the same orientation, we will have a solution each time that the sums of the coefficients c_k and b_k of such a group are zero. We will call it a quasi-trivial solution and such a group a saturated group. It is immediately recognised that a group is saturated independently of the orientation of its plies, which means that quasi-trivial solutions determine in reality only a stacking sequence, but not the orientations of each layer. Consequently, mechanically speaking, each quasi-trivial solution corresponds to $g-1$ infinities of different solutions, where g is the number of saturated groups, that is of possible different orientations. All them are quasi-homogeneous, but are distinguished by the final mechanical properties of the laminate. Evidently, for the same laminate, it is in general possible to find different quasi-trivial solutions, with different numbers of orientations. Before going on to show the method to find quasi-trivial solutions, it is worth listing some properties of this class of solutions.

A saturated group must have plies both in the upper and in the lower part of the middle plane; in fact, let us suppose that a group of plies, all being in the same part with respect to middle plane, is saturated with respect to coefficients c_k ; then, the sum of its b_k coefficients is different from zero, due to the fact that these last are anti-symmetric and linearly variable along the thickness. Such a stacking sequence can have the same membrane and bending behaviour, but should not be uncoupled.

The preceding property implies that the lower theoretical number of plies in a saturated group is two. Consequently, the maximum number of different saturated group, that is of different orientations, in a N -plies laminate is strictly less than $N/2$. In fact, excepted the case of coefficients c_k null (see below), in a saturated group there must be at least 3 plies, in order to have a null sum both of coefficients c_k and b_k , and this automatically limits the number of different orientations to less than $N/2$. In addition, as the coefficients c_k have null sum also on one half of the laminate, symmetric solutions are possible, and the number of different orientations, for what said above, is strictly limited to $N/4$. Moreover, a symmetric solution is possible only if a saturated group of c_k coefficients exists in only one half of the stacking sequence.

Another important property of such class of solutions, is that a solution with g different orientations descends from another with $g-1$ groups. As a consequence of this property, if a

laminates has not quasi-trivial solutions with g different orientations, it will not have quasi-trivial solutions also for more than g orientations. This circumstance gives a criterion for ending the procedure of the search for quasi-trivial solutions.

It must be stressed out also the existence of particular cases in quasi-trivial solutions. In fact, in some cases, it occurs that a coefficient c_k is zero, and consequently also its symmetric, c_{-k} . Then, by virtue of the anti-symmetry of coefficients b_k , a quasi-trivial solution is immediately identified, corresponding to a saturated group formed by these two symmetric plies. It is worth noticing that, due to the fact that coefficients c_k are quadratically varying and that they are symmetric, not more than two plies in a laminate can have null coefficient c_k . To find laminates which have this property, it is sufficient to pose equal to zero the expressions giving coefficients c_k in Eqs. (13). The first five laminates that can enjoy this property are the laminates with 2, 7, 26, 97 and 362 plies, where the plies with null coefficient c_k are respectively the number 1, 2, 8, 28 and 105 from the bottom, and their symmetric ones.

In the following, we will give a label, namely a number, to each different saturated group in a laminate, beginning from zero. To easily detect equal solutions, each sequence is ordered, in the sense that, proceeding from the bottom of the stacking sequence, the first orientation encountered is always labelled by 0, then the second by 1, the third by 2, and so on.

QUASI-HOMOGENEOUS LAMINATES FOR THERMO-ELASTIC EFFECTS

It is possible to perform for thermoelastic effects an analysis similar to the preceding one. Classically, we will consider a linearly through thickness varying thermal field, which is the real situation of a laminate constituted by plies of the same material, subjected to a difference of temperature between the upper and the lower surface, once the thermal flux is stationary. It must be stressed out that now the assumption of all the plies with the same physical properties has now a physical relevance. Moreover, the assumed conditions are those used in the manufacturing process of laminates, so they have a fundamental importance in practice.

We assume the following distribution of temperature across the thickness :

$$\tau(z) = \tau_0 + \frac{2\Delta\tau}{h} z, \quad (14)$$

where τ_0 is the value corresponding to middle plane, $z = 0$, and $2\Delta\tau$ is the difference of temperature between the two faces. The general behaviour in the presence of such a thermal field is given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 \\ \boldsymbol{\chi} \end{Bmatrix} - \tau_0 \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{R} \\ \mathbf{S} \end{Bmatrix} - \frac{2\Delta\tau}{h} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{S} \\ \mathbf{V} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{R} , \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{V} are three second order tensors describing thermal stresses for the laminate in stretching, coupling and bending respectively. Likewise in the case of elastic constants, one can write down the polar components of \mathbf{R} , \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{V} : for a generic second order plane tensor \mathbf{L} we have its Cartesian components expressed as :

$$L_1 = T + R \cos 2\Phi; \quad L_2 = T - R \cos 2\Phi; \quad L_{12} = R \sin 2\Phi. \quad (16)$$

The conditions of quasi-homogeneity for thermal effects are :

$$\frac{\mathbf{R}}{h} = 12 \frac{\mathbf{V}}{h^3}, \quad \mathbf{S} = \mathbf{0} \quad (17)$$

which give, in the case of identical plies,

$$\bar{\mathbf{T}} = \tilde{\mathbf{T}} = \mathbf{T}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{T}} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (18)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{h} \bar{\mathbf{R}} e^{2i\bar{\Phi}} = \frac{12}{h^3} \tilde{\mathbf{R}} e^{2i\tilde{\Phi}} &\Rightarrow \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} = \frac{4}{h^3} \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^3 - z_k^3); \\ \hat{\mathbf{R}} e^{2i\hat{\Phi}} = 0 &\Rightarrow \sum_{k=-p}^p e^{2i\delta_k} (z_{k+1}^2 - z_k^2) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

It is apparent that Eqs. (19) correspond exactly to Eqs. (10₂₋₄). Together with the fact that in Eqs. (10) only two sets of coefficient, b_k and c_k , exists for four equations, this implies that there is a perfect coincidence between elastic and thermoelastic quasi-trivial solutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The above mentioned properties of quasi-trivial solutions have been widely used in the formulation of an automatic algorithm able to find all quasi-trivial solutions. By means of this, we have analysed a certain number of laminates, and found for each one the total number of quasi-trivial solutions for the problem of quasi-homogeneity.

A question arises from consideration of these results : are all the solutions effectively independent solutions ? Take for instance a solution of the kind [0 1 2 2 1 0] and another of the kind [0 1 1 1 1 0]. It is apparent that the second one can be considered as a particular case of the first one, when for the third and fourth layer it is assumed the same orientation of the saturated group labelled as 1. So, we can consider the second one as a derived solution, and the first one as a pure, or independent, solution. We have decided to consider only the independent solutions as real distinct ones. In effect, under a mathematical point of view, two dependent solutions are the same one : they differentiate themselves only for having chosen the same orientation for two or more distinct groups.

Table 1: Number and type of quasi-trivial independent solutions.

N. of plies	Total solutions		2 orientations		3 orientations		4 orientations		5 orientations		6 orientations	
	generic.	sym.	generic.	sym.	generic.	sym.	generic.	sym.	generic.	sym.	generic.	sym.
7	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
8	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11	3	2	3	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
12	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
13	3	2	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
14	2	1	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
15	4	0	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
16	8	1	5	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
17	23	0	15	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	5	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
19	52	0	30	0	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

20	40	0	30	0	9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
21	44	2	31	0	13	2	0	0	0	0	0	0
22	130	3	17	2	98	1	13	0	2	0	0	0
23	594	1	95	1	499	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
24	167	0	140	0	26	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
25	2352	0	163	0	2132	0	57	0	0	0	0	0
26	1495	7	54	0	1059	2	354	3	26	2	2	0
27	1282	1	86	1	918	0	256	0	21	0	1	0
28	5902	3	203	0	4788	1	869	2	33	0	6	0
29	45441	0	61	0	37747	0	7546	0	87	0	0	0
30	6146	3	53	0	5552	0	512	3	29	0	0	0

The results are summarised in Table 1, where they are ranged by total number of pure solutions, and by pure solutions with 2, 3, 4, 5, or 6 different orientations. In addition, for each case, the number of symmetric pure solutions is detailed. At a first glance, it is surprising to notice that, contrarily to what is commonly thought, symmetric solutions are only a little part of the whole. The number of solutions is rapidly increasing, but not monotonically.

Finally, we have considered the existence of so-called anti-symmetric solutions, i.e. solutions with two orientations characterised by having a stacking sequence of the kind [0 1 1 0 1 0 0 1]. We have found that only laminates whose number of plies is a multiple of 4 can have quasi-trivial anti-symmetric solutions for the quasi-homogeneity problem. In Table 2, we show the number of anti-symmetric solutions as a function of the number of plies.

Table 2: Number of anti-symmetric solutions.

Number of layers	8	12	16	20	24	28
Anti-symmetric pure solutions	1	1	4	8	32	49

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

We have manufactured and tested some laminates designed according to the previous analysis. We have chosen a 19-layer plate. The single layer is a carbon-epoxy ply, with estimated elastic constants $E_1 = 131.9$ Gpa, $E_2 = 9.51$ Gpa, $G_{12} = 5.27$ Gpa and $\nu_{12} = 0.326$. The thickness of a single ply is 0.125 mm, for a total thickness of the plate of 2.375 mm.

For a 19-layer laminate, we have at our disposal 85 different quasi-trivial solutions, five of which are symmetric. We have selected the following non symmetric stacking sequence :

$$[0 \ 1 \ 0_5 \ 1 \ 0_5 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0_3].$$

The layers labelled by 0 are oriented at 0° , while those labelled by 1 are oriented at 90° . Hence the laminate, composed of orthotropic plies, should be orthotropic itself.

The experimental results, obtained from tensile tests, are shown in Table 3, along with predictions from the classical laminated plate theory. All the tests have confirmed that the components of coupling tensor \mathbf{B} were null. The results are rather satisfying, and theoretical predictions can be considered as confirmed by experimental results.

Table 3: Experimental results for the 19-layer plate.

	E_x [GPa]	E_y [GPa]	G_{xy} [GPa]	ν_{xy}
Membrane	106.8	34.4	4.8	0.075
Bending	97.5	35.2	4.0	0.085
CLPT estimate	106.7	35.5	5.3	0.088

CONCLUSIONS.

Using the polar representation of plane elasticity tensors, we have discovered a particular class of solutions to the problem of quasi-homogeneity, that we have named quasi-trivial solutions. In other words, we have found a general method to design the stacking sequence for a quasi-homogeneous laminate, without distinction between symmetric and non symmetric solutions. The quasi-trivial solutions have some important properties, from which we have formulated an algorithm able to find all them. The large number of solutions that we have found can be considered able to solve most of the problems found in practical applications.

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